

CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, AND PREVENTION OF ANGINA PECTORIS

¹Ermatov Farruxjon

²Juraboyev Ozodbek

³Umarov Sherali

Samarkand State Medical University, DKTF, Department of Internal Medicine, Cardiology and Functional Diagnostics, 2nd year clinical residents

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864297>

Introduction: Angina can manifest as a mild, non-distracting pain or can quickly develop into a strong, intense feeling of pressure in the precordial region. Angina is rarely described by the patients themselves as "pain". In most cases, patients complain of a feeling of discomfort behind the sternum, and the localization of these sensations can also vary. The feeling of discomfort can spread to the left shoulder and extend to the fingertips of the left hand. Pain may occur in the back, throat, lower jaw and teeth, radiating to the inner surface of the right arm. Sometimes this feeling of discomfort is localized in the upper abdomen. It is characteristic that with stable angina, pathological sensations are never localized above the ears and below the navel. Angina pectoris is a clinical syndrome characterized by discomfort or tightness in the precordial region, which is caused by transient myocardial ischemia without the development of infarction. In most cases, angina attacks develop against the background of physical or emotional stress and pass at rest or after sublingual administration of nitroglycerin. The diagnosis of the disease is established on the basis of clinical manifestations, ECG changes and various methods of visualization of myocardial ischemia. Treatment may include antiplatelet drugs, nitrates, beta-blockers, calcium channel blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, statins, coronary angioplasty or coronary artery bypass grafting.

Research methods and materials: The narrowing of blood vessels in atherosclerosis is not completely static, the size of the vascular lumen is affected by changes in vascular tone, which is usually present in all people; It has been found that in most patients, angina attacks occur in the morning hours, when there is an increase in vascular tone. In addition, endothelial dysfunction may contribute to changes in arterial tone: for example, in the endothelium affected by atherosclerosis, a "catecholamine surge" causes more vasoconstriction than vasodilation (the normal response).

When myocardial ischemia occurs, a decrease in blood pH is observed in the coronary sinus, the release of potassium ions into the extracellular space, the accumulation of lactate, changes in the ECG are noted, and a decrease in ventricular contractility (systolic and diastolic) is

Fevral, 2025-Yil

noted. During an attack of angina pectoris, an increase in diastolic pressure in the LV is usually observed, which is sometimes accompanied by congestion in the lungs and shortness of breath. The exact mechanism responsible for the feeling of shortness of breath during an angina attack is unknown, but stimulation of nerve endings by metabolites formed during hypoxia may be involved.

Results The frequency of attacks can vary from several attacks per day to prolonged periods of absence of clinical symptoms lasting weeks, months, or years. The frequency of attacks can increase (called progressive angina), which leads to myocardial infarction or death. Conversely, attacks can gradually decrease or disappear, if adequate collateral coronary circulation develops, a necrotic focus appears at the site of the ischemic area, or heart failure or intermittent claudication develops, limiting activity.

Nocturnal angina attacks are caused by changes in breathing, heart rate, and blood pressure that occur during sleep. Nocturnal angina attacks can also be a manifestation of left ventricular failure, which is equivalent to nocturnal attacks of shortness of breath. In the supine position, venous return is increased, which leads to myocardial stretching and increased myocardial tension, which in turn increases myocardial oxygen demand.

Rest angina is angina that occurs spontaneously in the supine position, but not necessarily at night. It is usually accompanied by a slight increase in heart rate and sometimes a significant increase in blood pressure, which, accordingly, increases the demand for myocardial oxygen. On the other hand, an increase in blood pressure and heart rate can provoke the development of an angina attack, and they can be the result of myocardial ischemia in response to rupture of atherosclerotic plaque and formation of a thrombus in a coronary artery. If an angina attack lasts a long time, the imbalance between myocardial oxygen demand and supply increases, which increases the likelihood of myocardial infarction. If the patient has a normal resting ECG and is able to exercise, an exercise stress ECG is performed. In men with chest discomfort suggestive of angina, the sensitivity of the stress ECG is approximately 70% and the specificity is approximately 80% (1). These values are somewhat lower for women. In addition, women with coronary artery disease are more likely to have resting ECG changes than men (32% vs. 23%). Despite the high sensitivity of the exercise stress test, false-negative results are possible in severe forms of coronary heart disease (main or three-vessel disease). A positive test is the basis for further investigation. In patients with an atypical clinical presentation, a negative exercise test usually excludes angina and cardiovascular disease.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

Stress myocardial imaging is performed in conditions where the resting ECG is abnormal, as false-positive ST-segment elevations are common on the stress ECG. Exercise or pharmacological therapy (eg, dobutamine and dipyridamole infusions) may be used. Imaging techniques include stress echocardiography, myocardial perfusion imaging with single-photon emission CT (SPECT) or PET, and stress MRI. The choice of imaging technique depends on its availability in the clinic and the experience of the investigators. Imaging techniques allow assessment of LV contractile function at rest and in response to stress, identification of areas of ischemia, myocardial infarction, and viable myocardium, and localization and distribution of the risk zone. Stress echocardiography also allows the diagnosis of mitral regurgitation associated with ischemic papillary muscle dysfunction.

Conclusion: Electron beam CT allows us to measure the amount of calcium in atherosclerotic plaque in the coronary artery. The calcium index is associated with the risk of developing coronary artery disease. However, because calcium can be detected in the absence of significant stenosis, this index does not correlate well with the need for PCI or CABG. Based on these findings, the American Heart Association recommends that CT be performed only in a limited population of patients and in conjunction with clinical and medical history to assess the risk of fatal or nonfatal MI (4). These groups may include asymptomatic patients with an intermediate 10-year risk estimate for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (10–20%) and symptomatic patients with inconclusive stress test results. The use of electron beam CT is essential to exclude serious coronary disease in patients presenting to the emergency department with atypical symptoms, normal troponin levels, and a low probability of hemodynamically significant coronary artery disease.

REFERENCES

1. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

4. Begbudiye M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
5. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
6. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
7. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
8. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
9. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
10. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
11. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
12. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
14. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

16. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
18. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
19. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
20. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
21. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
22. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
23. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
24. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.
25. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.
26. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
27. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.
28. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 63-69.
29. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 56-62.

Fevral, 2025-Yil

30. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 173-178.
31. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 198-204.
32. Solovyova Y. et al. Protective-adaptive complexes with codependency //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 70-75.
33. Solovyova Y. et al. Suicide prevention in adolescents with mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 303-308.
34. Solovyova Y. et al. The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 212-217.
35. Spirkina M. et al. Integrated approach to correcting neurocognitive defects in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 76-81.

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH